

LAMINATE PROCESSING EFFECT ON MICROVOIDS AND HYDRAULIC FLUID ABSORPTION OF QUARTZ/BMI LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Use of composite materials in complex and robust systems, such as aircraft fuselage and load-bearing structures, is becoming more prevalent as analysis and manufacturing techniques improve. Bismaleimide (BMI) resin with Quartz (AQ581) fiber reinforcement is one such composite material used in products requiring a high glass transition temperature and/or favorable electrical properties such as a low dielectric constant. Laminate fabrication conditions, such as applied cure pressure, can have a significant effect on the liquid absorption characteristics and microvoid formation throughout composite laminates. Long-term composite degradation due to environmental effects, such as absorption of water and other liquid contaminants, must be considered as products with longer service-life become increasingly desirable. Unlike water absorption, the long-term hydraulic fluid absorption by fiber-reinforced laminates has not been studied extensively. Various composite components used in aircrafts are often exposed to different types of hydraulic fluids, which may lead to anomalous absorption behavior over the service life of the composite. Accurate predictive absorption models are important in scheduling necessary repair or replacement during the service life of composites.

In this paper, hydraulic fluid absorption characteristics of Quartz/BMI laminates manufactured at different cure pressures are presented. The composite samples are immersed into hydraulic fluid at room temperature, and were not subjected to any prior degradation. To generate process-induced microvoids, all prepregs were conditioned in an environmental chamber at 99% relative humidity at room temperature for a period of 24 hours prior to laminate fabrication. The laminates were then manufactured at cure pressures of 10, 30, 50, and 70 psi via a hot-press. The laminates are shown to have different levels of microvoids ranging from 7.9% to 13.9%, which are also observed to affect the absorption dynamics considerably. The laminates also exhibited clear non-Fickian absorption behavior. A one-dimensional hindered diffusion model (HDM) was successful in predicting the hydraulic fluid absorption behavior. A nearly 50% decrease in maximum mass gain and 8% increase in hindrance coefficient as fabrication pressure increased was observed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Variations in laminate processing conditions, such as fabrication cure pressure, can have a significant effect on microstructural features of fiber-reinforced composites (i.e. fiber volume fraction and void fraction) and consequently influence their mechanical properties and long term durability. Although a low void fraction is required for primary aircraft structures, secondary structures can be manufactured using lower cost alternatives which might induce increased variability of laminate microstructure. Predictive models that consider fabrication cure pressure can be useful in the design and manufacturing stages, or when scheduling repair or replacement of contaminated composites during the service life of secondary aircraft structures.

Bismaleimide resin (BMI), such as HexPly® F650, with quartz (AQ581) fiber reinforcement is a high performance composite material commonly used in aerospace applications in products requiring a high glass transition temperature as well as excellent mechanical and electromagnetic properties [1]. Although primary structures and load-bearing structures must be manufactured with limited defects, several secondary aircraft structures can be manufactured by lower-cost alternatives that may increase

variability of the laminate microstructure. Research into the effect of process-induced defects, such as microvoids, has been commonplace for several decades [2-6]. However, the synergistic effects and interaction between microvoids and other microstructural features, such as fiber volume fraction, have not been studied as extensively. Previous works report various absorption and mechanical property effects as a result of changing void content [2]. Some common methods of varying the void fraction is by changing autoclave or hot-press pressure, modifying cure cycle temperature ramps and holds, or by debulking or not debulking prepregs prior to laminate fabrication [3-5]. These all carry the drawback of significantly altering the fiber volume fraction of a laminate, some by as much as 20% [6]. In this paper, the interaction between laminate fabrication pressure and prepreg conditioning on the formation and distribution of microvoids and absorption characteristics of hydraulic fluid will be presented.

As composite materials are utilized in systems requiring a long service-life, accurate characterization of process-induced degradation of polymer properties becomes more critical. More specifically, predictive models could be used in the design and manufacturing stages of component fabrication in that prepreg preconditioning and laminate fabrication pressure could be tailored for a specific application or desired outcome. Moisture absorption behavior and laminate degradation of fiber-reinforced epoxy laminates has been studied extensively [7,8]. Moisture absorption behavior of BMI resins has not been investigated to the same level as epoxy-based systems, although it has been addressed occasionally [9-12]. This is most likely due to the relatively specialized applications of BMI systems when compared to epoxy-based systems. Effects of hydraulic fluid absorption on epoxy or BMI-based systems are even more limited [13]. The most common absorption model applied to composite laminates is the one-dimensional case of Fickian second law of diffusion and associated correction factors for edge effects. The widespread use of Fickian-based models partially stems from their ease of use as the ASTM D30 committee recommends the Fickian-based characterization, outlined in the D5229 standard. This approach is suitable when characterizing through-the-thickness absorption for single-phase, Fickian solid materials. In many cases, these methods can be insufficient when investigating anisotropic materials or samples with finite dimensions [14]. Frequently the use of so-called non-Fickian diffusion models is necessary for polymer systems. Common non-Fickian models include the “Langmuir-type” model of diffusion and time-varying diffusivity models [15,16]. Grace and Altan [17,18] recently developed a three-dimensional hindered diffusion model (HDM) that considers material anisotropy by proposing an alternative mechanism for anomalous moisture uptake behavior based on polymer-penetrant interaction. Previously this model has been used successfully to model anomalous moisture uptake for quartz/BMI systems [19].

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material used in this study is a Bismaleimide resin, trade name HexPly[®] F650, reinforced with an eight-harness satin weave quartz fabric, style 581 [1]. This section will focus on the preparation procedure for conditioning the prepregs, the laminate fabrication method, as well as the experimental method for determining the laminate fiber volume fraction, void fraction, and immersion set-up for hydraulic fluid absorption.

2.1 Prepreg Preparation and Laminate Fabrication

All prepregs were preconditioned in an environmental chamber at room temperature, i.e. 25°C, for a period of 24 hours prior to fabrication. The relative humidity level was set at 99%, which resulted in a prepreg moisture content of 0.57% wt. Eight-ply thick laminates were fabricated from the conditioned prepregs at cure pressures of 68.9 kPa (10 psi), 206.8 kPa (30 psi), 344.7 kPa (50 psi), or 482.6 kPa (70 psi) via a hot-press. The conditioned prepregs were cured in accordance with the recommended temperature curing cycle by the material supplier (Hexcel): (i) Apply specified cure pressure at ambient temperature and hold for complete fabrication cycle; (ii) Hold at 38°C for 30 min; (iii) raise the temperature to 191°C at a ramp rate of 3°C/min; (iv) hold for 4 hours, and (v) cool down to 65°C prior to removal from hot-press. A graphical representation of the cure cycle is shown in Figure 1. An eight-hour post cure at 232°C was performed on the fabricated laminates by raising the temperature from room temperature to 191°C at a ramp rate of 5°C/min, followed by a subsequent ramp from 191°C to 232°C at a ramp rate of 1.5°C/min, hold for eight hours, and cool down to room

temperature. For hydraulic fluid immersion characterization, six individual test specimens with approximate planar dimensions of 31.5 mm by 31.5 mm were cut from the original test panels using a high-speed wet diamond saw. Once the specimens were cut to their final size, they were dried in a vacuum-oven at 40°C until an equilibrium dry weight was achieved. The absorption samples were started from the dried condition to establish a baseline for the specimens and enables accurate determination of absorption parameters as it removes any ambiguity from unknown initial moisture in the laminates.

Figure 1: Manufacturer suggested cure cycle for HexPly® F650 BMI resin that was utilized for the laminates in this study. Solid black line represents the cure temperature profile.

2.1 Fiber Volume Fraction and Void Fraction

Five rectangular specimens from each quartz/BMI laminate were used to determine the laminate fiber volume fraction and void fraction in accordance with the procedure described by Anderson and Altan [20,21]. The approximate planar dimensions of each specimen were 31.8 mm by 12.7 mm. The density of the bulk composite specimens was determined by suspending the samples in Cargill Labs 2490 kg/m³ Heavy Liquid diluted by water. The matrix density was determined by a similar method of suspending a void free matrix specimen in a water/glycerol solution. A fluid pycnometer was used to measure the suspended solution density, which correlates to the bulk specimen density at a specific solution density. The fiber reinforcement density was determined by the use of a helium pycnometer. The weight fraction of both the fiber reinforcement and matrix was determined by using the acid digestion method recommended by ASTM D3171-11, Procedure G. With the resulting constituent densities and weight fractions, the void fraction (V_v) and fiber fraction (V_f) of the specimens were calculated as recommended by ASTM D3171-11, using Equations 1 and 2, respectively.

$$V_v = 100 - \rho_c \left(\frac{W_f}{\rho_f} + \frac{W_m}{\rho_m} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$V_f = \frac{\rho_c W_f}{\rho_f} \quad (2)$$

where ρ_c , ρ_f , and ρ_m are the densities of the bulk composite, fiber reinforcement, and matrix, respectively; and W_f and W_m are the weight fractions of the fiber reinforcement and matrix, respectively. The precision of this procedure in determining the void fraction in a composite sample has been reported by Anderson and Altan [20] to be $\pm 0.22\%$.

2.2 Hydraulic Fluid Absorption Models

From the full-dry condition, the specimens were placed in sealed glass containers filled with hydraulic fluid. The hydraulic fluid used in this study was Castrol Brayco 881, which is a synthetic hydrocarbon-based fluid commonly used in aerospace applications and which conforms to the military standard MIL-PRF-87257A. Castrol Brayco 881 is characterized by a specific gravity of 0.84 and a

kinematic viscosity of 7.2 cSt at 40°C. The glass containers were placed in a constant-temperature water bath at 25°C. The specimens were periodically removed from immersion, surface fluid removed with a lint-free cloth, and weighed with a high-precision analytical balance. The time required to dry and weigh samples was deducted from the total fluid exposure time. Typically the entire procedure of removal, drying, weighing, and re-immersion was less than 10 minutes per specimen series. The percentage mass gain, $M_{exp}(t)$, of each sample is determined by:

$$M_{exp}(t) = 100 \left[\frac{m_i(t) - m_o}{m_o} \right] \quad (3)$$

where $m_i(t)$ is the measured instantaneous weight of the specimen, and m_o is the initial, full-dry weight of the specimen after desorption in the vacuum-oven. All gravimetric data reported in this study is an average of six specimens with uncertainty levels calculated using 95% confidence interval.

The three-dimensional, anisotropic hindered diffusion model developed by Grace and Altan [16] is an extension of one-dimensional, Langmuir-type diffusion model. The methods of absorption parameter recovery as well as the utility and accuracy of the HDM have been investigated for moisture and hydraulic fluid absorption in recent publications [12,17-18]. The governing equations for the three-dimensional, anisotropic hindered diffusion model can be expressed as,

$$D_x \frac{\partial^2 n}{\partial x^2} + D_y \frac{\partial^2 n}{\partial y^2} + D_z \frac{\partial^2 n}{\partial z^2} = \frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial N}{\partial t} \quad (4a)$$

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial t} = \gamma n - \beta N \quad (4b)$$

where D_x , D_y , and D_z are the diffusion coefficient in the x , y , and z directions, respectively, n is the unbound molecules per unit volume, N is the bound molecules per unit volume, γ is the probability per unit time that an unbound molecule will become bound, and β is the probability per unit time that an bound molecule will become mobile. Analytical solution for bound moisture concentration $N(x,t)$ and unbound moisture concentration $n(x,t)$ of Equation 4 for one-dimensional Langmuir-type diffusion is also given by Carter and Kibler [14]. To find the fluid content by weight percentage, the sum of $N(x,t)$ and $n(x,t)$ is integrated over the laminate thickness and the result is shown in Equation 5a.

$$M(t) = M_\infty \left\{ 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{i=1}^{=(\text{odd})} \frac{\eta_i^+ \exp(-\eta_i^- t) - \eta_i^- \exp(-\eta_i^+ t)}{i^2(\eta_i^+ - \eta_i^-)} + \frac{8}{\pi^2} (K\mu) \sum_{i=1}^{=(\text{odd})} \frac{\exp(-\eta_i^- t) - \exp(-\eta_i^+ t)}{(\eta_i^+ - \eta_i^-)} \right\} \quad (5a)$$

where,

$$\eta_i^\pm = \frac{1}{2} [(Ki^2 + \gamma + \beta) \pm \sqrt{(Ki^2 + \gamma + \beta)^2 - 4K\beta i^2}] \quad K = \frac{\pi^2 D}{h^2} \quad \mu = \frac{\beta}{\beta + \gamma} \quad (5b)$$

$M(t)$ is the weight percent of absorbed fluid at time t , M_∞ is the equilibrium fluid weight percent and μ is the hindrance coefficient, which is a non-dimensional parameter governing the degree of non-Fickian behavior for the material. Absorption becomes purely Fickian when the hindrance coefficient, $\mu=1$, and absorption becomes more anomalous as μ approaches 0.

3 RESULTS

This section will focus on the results of this study, which will be broken up into the following four categories: microstructure, experimental data, model fit, and fabrication pressure effects.

3.1 Microstructure Results

The average fiber volume fraction and void fraction with 95% confidence interval for the quartz/BMI laminates in this study is shown in Table 1.

Fabrication Pressure (kPa [psi])	Laminate Thickness (mm)	Fiber Volume Fraction	Void Fraction
68.9 (10)	2.07 ± 0.09	52.3 ± 5.2	13.9 ± 3.2
206.8 (30)	1.81 ± 0.04	64.9 ± 2.6	11.7 ± 1.3
344.7 (50)	1.74 ± 0.05	65.6 ± 2.6	10.0 ± 1.2
482.6 (70)	1.69 ± 0.02	64.1 ± 1.0	7.9 ± 1.1

Table 1: Fiber volume fraction and void fraction of quartz/BMI laminates. Note: Intervals are associated with 95% confidence for five specimens.

It was observed from Table 1 that the fiber volume fraction was statistically similar for all laminates fabricated above 206.8 kPa. Increasing the fabrication pressure resulted in a near-linear decrease in void fraction, which is illustrated in Figure 2. Additionally, it was observed that as the fabrication pressure increased, the variation in void fraction decreased, as indicated by the smaller confidence intervals in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Fabrication pressure effect on laminate void fraction. Note: Error bars represent 95% confidence interval for $n = 5$ samples.

Select SEM images that are representative of the laminates in this study are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: SEM images at 35X magnification of microvoid formation for quartz/BMI laminates fabricated at (a) 68.9 kPa, (b) 206.8 kPa, (c) 344.7 kPa, and (d) 482.6 kPa.

The SEM images shown in Figure 3 indicate the formation of large-scale voids, primarily located in the intra-tow regions and ply-to-ply interface. Generally, the spatial void distribution throughout

the thickness of the laminate did not change as a result of fabrication pressure. As the fabrication pressure increased, the void morphology became more elongated, i.e. void aspect ratio increased. This observation is highlighted by red rectangles in Figures 3(a) and 3(d).

3.2 Experimental Data Results

The hydraulic fluid absorption of quartz/BMI laminates with time for different fabrication pressures is shown in Figure 4. The experimental data in Figure 4 is for about 9 months of immersion in hydraulic fluid.

Figure 4: Hydraulic fluid mass gain at 25°C of eight-ply quartz/BMI laminates fabricated at different cure pressures. Specimen planar dimensions are 31.5 mm by 31.5 mm. Note: Error bars represent 95% confidence interval for $n = 6$ samples.

As fabrication pressure increased, the hydraulic fluid mass gain decreased. Since fluid absorption is a matrix-dominated phenomenon, this was expected because as fabrication pressure increased, the laminates featured a higher fiber volume fraction and lower void fractions. Additionally, it was observed that as fabrication pressure increased, the sampling variation in the experimental mass gain measurements decreased, which is indicated by the confidence intervals in Figure 4. After the study duration, the fluid content of the laminates ranged from 7.7% wt. to 3.9% wt. as fabrication pressure increased.

3.3 Model Fit Results

The hydraulic fluid absorption data of quartz/BMI laminates fabricated from conditioned preregs at different cure pressures was fit to a one-dimensional hindered diffusion model as described by Equations 4 and 5. The model predictions can be used in estimating long-term effects of fluid absorption, and is shown in this fashion in Figure 5. The absorption parameters determined by the hindered diffusion model are shown in Table 2. From Table 2, it was observed that it took less than 48 hours of immersion for the laminates to reach 50% saturation. Observations on the absorption parameters of Table 2 will be presented in the next section.

Figure 5: Long-term prediction for hydraulic fluid absorption of quartz/BMI laminates fabricated at different cure pressures.

Absorption Parameter		68.9 kPa	206.8 kPa	344.7 kPa	482.6 kPa
D_z	mm ² /hr.	9.87E-03	8.09E-03	8.71E-03	9.55E-03
μ	-	0.68	0.77	0.75	0.74
M_∞	% wt.	7.75	4.73	4.08	3.94
Number of Iterations	-	4353	7181	9651	9394
RMS Error	-	0.0406	0.0216	0.0185	0.0173
Time to 50% saturation	hr ^{0.5}	6.61	5.37	5.16	4.97

Table 2: Comparison of one-dimensional hindered diffusion parameters at 25°C for quartz/BMI laminates fabricated at different cure pressures.

3.4 Effect of Laminate Fabrication Pressure on Absorption Behavior

Figure 6 highlights the effect of laminate fabrication pressure on the through-the-thickness diffusion coefficient. Similarly, Figure 7 highlights the effect of laminate fabrication pressure on the maximum mass gain and hindrance coefficient.

Figure 6: Effect of fabrication pressure on the diffusion coefficient of hydraulic fluid absorption for eight-ply quartz/BMI laminates.

Figure 7: Effect of fabrication pressure on the maximum mass gain (■) and hindrance coefficient (○) for eight-ply quartz/BMI laminates.

From Figure 6, it was observed that the highest diffusion coefficient was observed in the laminate fabricated at low pressures (68.9 kPa). This may be due to the significantly lower fiber volume fraction of the low fabrication pressure laminate when compared to the other laminates in this study. From Figure 7, it was observed the maximum mass gain occurred at lower fabrication pressures. This is also associated with a higher void fraction. This may be due to the voids within the laminate acting as storage cells for hydraulic fluid. Laminates fabricated at a low cure pressure demonstrated the most anomalous hydraulic fluid absorption behavior, as indicated by the lowest hindrance coefficient. The hydraulic fluid absorption behavior was not significantly different when fabrication pressure was greater than 206.8 kPa. Increasing the fabrication pressure from 68.9 kPa to 482.6 kPa resulted in a nearly 50% reduction in maximum mass gain and approximately 8% increase in hindrance coefficient.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effect of fabrication pressure on conditioned quartz/BMI prepregs on the formation of microvoids and hydraulic fluid absorption characteristics was introduced. Increasing the fabrication pressure resulted in a near-linear reduction in void fraction from 13.9% to 7.9%. SEM images revealed the formation of large scale voids that were predominantly located in the ply-to-ply interface and inter-tow regions. Hydraulic fluid absorption behavior was found to be very sensitive to the laminate microstructure. After about 9 months of immersion in hydraulic fluid, the fluid content of the laminates ranged from 3.9% wt. to 7.7% wt. A one-dimensional hindered diffusion model was successful in predicting the absorption behavior for the quartz/BMI laminates. The diffusion coefficient was highest when the laminates were fabricated at the lowest pressure (68.9 kPa). Additionally, the laminate fabricated at low pressure displayed the most anomalous absorption behavior. A nearly 50% decrease in maximum mass gain and about 8% increase in hindrance coefficient as fabrication pressure increased was observed.

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